

VERBALIZATION OF THE CONCEPT "BEAUTY / UGLINESS" IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract

This study is devoted to the problem of comparative analysis of subjective-evaluative, associative and cognitive-metaphorical meanings in the Uzbek and English languages combined with the linguistic-cognitive understanding of the concept of "beauty/ugliness" in the minds of speakers. The article analyzes the use of the concept of linguistic culture in Uzbek and English culture, in particular, the lexical-semantic expressions of the concept of "beauty/ugliness" in Uzbek and English languages. In the lexical-semantic research of the concept of "beauty/ugliness", the origin of the total lexemes collected around the concept in the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", the study of lexical meaning data, their context Uzbek and devoted to the study of appropriate forms in English.

Key words: linguistics, comparative linguistics, beauty, ugliness, concept, linguocultural, lexical unit, lexeme, translation, morphological category, word group scientific translation, literary translation, style, talent of translator.

Annotation

Ушбу тадқиқоти сўзловчилар онгида "гўзаллик/хунуклик" концептининг лингвокогнитив тушунчаси билан бирлаштирилган ўзбек ва инглиз тилларидаги субъектив-баҳо, ассоциатив ва когнитив-метафорик маъноларни қиёсий таҳлил қилиш муаммосига бағишланган. Мақолда лингвокультурология тushunchasini o'zbek va ingliz til madaniyatida ishlatilishi, xususan, "go'zallik/xunuklik" konseptining o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi leksik-semantik ifodalari tahlil qilinadi. "Go'zallik/xunuklik" konseptini leksik-semantik tadqiq qilishda "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati"dagi konsept atrofida to'plangan jami leksemalarning kelib chiqishi, leksik ma'no ma'lumotlarini o'rganish, ularning kontekstga o'zbek va ingliz tilidagi mos shakllarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: tilshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik, go'zallik, xunuklik, konsept, lingvokulturologiya, leksik birlik, leksema, tarjima, morfologik kategoriya, so'z turkumlari.

Данное исследование посвящено проблеме сопоставительного анализа субъектно-оценочных, ассоциативных и когнитивно-метафорических значений в узбекском и английском языках в сочетании с лингвокогнитивным пониманием концепта «красота/уродство» в сознании носителей. В статье анализируется использование концепта лингвокультуры в узбекской и английской культурах, в частности лексико-семантические выражения концепта «красота/уродство» в узбекском и английском языках. При лексико-семантическом исследовании концепта «красота/некрасивость», происхождении всей совокупности лексем, собранных вокруг концепта в «Толковом

словаре узбекского языка», изучении данных лексического значения, их контекста узбекского и посвященных изучение соответствующих форм в английском языке.

Ключевые слова: языкознание, сравнительное языкознание, красота, уродство, концепт, лингвокультурология, лексическая единица, лексема, перевод, морфологическая категория, группа слов.

Introduction: The concepts analyzed and explored in this article are fundamental to most language cultures around the world. Along with the "goodness/evil" contrast, the "beauty/ugliness" contrast is one of the defining paradigms in the formation of modern linguistic, cultural and psychological perception of the world by man.

In order to understand the functioning of both language and society, it is necessary to observe and understand all aspects of the actualization of the meaning of "beauty/ugliness" concepts, not only synchronically, but also diachronically. The primary goal of this article is to review in detail the meaning of the concept of "beauty/ugliness" based on the historical method of knowing, as well as to analyze these concepts by analytically comparing different linguistic and cultural layers.

The main tasks of our research are as follows: 1) systematization of knowledge about understanding the concepts of "beauty/ugliness" in Uzbek and English languages; 2) on the example of artistic texts (sentences taken from artistic works listed in Uzbek and English explanatory dictionaries) to determine the peculiarities of the use of these concepts in Uzbek and English languages.

The term concept appeared in Uzbek linguistics much later than in Western languages. According to the Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, concepts are units of thought. The article on concepts also notes that the exact definition of the concept is still controversial, as there are different approaches to the term. Ontologically, there are three approaches to concept: concept as mental representation; concept as ability; concept as feeling.

Literature review: In Western linguistics, the concept is considered more as a term related to cognitive linguistics. At the same time, cognitive linguistics is not a single theory, but a complex of many approaches to language learning. It includes cognitive grammar (R.Langaker, L.Talmy) [8] and constructive grammar (C.Fillmore, P.Kay, A.Goldberg, J.Lakoff, W.Kroft, B.Bergen), cognitive semantics, they address different aspects of cognitive semantics. Human thinking activities such as representing knowledge and constructing meanings.

Cognitive semantics, in turn, includes the theory of conceptual metaphor (J. Lakoff, M. Johnson, R. Gibbs, M. Turner), the theory of mental spaces (B. Dunsiger, S. Coulson), the theory of conceptual integration (J. Lakoff, W. Croft, B. Bergen). Also, such an approach as cognitive lexical semantics, which includes the theory of basic polysemy and the theory of lexical concepts and cognitive models (V. Evans, A. Tyler)[7].

Research Methodology: This study is devoted to the problem of comparative analysis of subjective-evaluative, associative and cognitive-metaphorical meanings in the Uzbek and English languages combined with the linguistic-cognitive understanding of the concept of "beauty/ugliness" in the minds of speakers. One of the main tasks of our research is to compare the concepts of "beauty/ugliness" in Uzbek and English based on conceptual, figurative and value aspects.

If we consider the concept of "beauty" as a semantic field, then its conceptual center is a certain property of the object as a reality phenomenon that gives aesthetic pleasure to the beholder, otherwise it will be the meaning of "ugliness". A slightly more off-centered meaning

of "beauty" can be considered a characteristic of an attractive human figure. Finally, at the edge of this field is the meaning of "beauty", which expresses "satisfaction or pleasure in something."

Finally, at the edge of this field is the meaning of "beauty" as a participle expressing "satisfaction or pleasure in something" [9].

Based on the information from the dictionary "Macmillan English Dictionary", we came to the following conclusion: The central values of the concept of "beauty/ugliness" in the English language are: a perfect example, a representative of something; beauty as a characteristic of the human form, approving exclamatory meanings ("You are beautiful!"), an unusual and striking example of something, and a distinctive and useful characteristic or quality of something (it takes very little work to start a project; this is its beauty)[6].

"Ugliness" is also an aesthetic concept, and it represents the opposite of beauty, features, things and events that are contrary to human beauty, honor, dignity and ideal visions. "Ugliness" causes various negative feelings, unpleasant mood, regret and hatred in a person, leaves an unpleasant impression [11].

Notably, in the English-speaking world there are two different terms for male and female beauty - beautiful, "pretty" (about a woman) and handsome, "sute" (about a man).

However, in the Uzbek language we can find several words that express "beauty/ugliness" concepts. The figurative meaning of the term "beauty" in the Uzbek language is very wide, so we will highlight only a part of the most characteristic metaphors for beauty in the Uzbek language environment.

In order to more fully reveal the conceptual meaning of the selected concept, we will also have to refer to synonym dictionaries. In them, we find the following words expressing the concept of "beauty": 1) beauty (pleasantness, delicacy, elegance, beauty, attractiveness, charm) as well as the characteristic of beautiful appearance, in general, a beautiful thing corresponds to the word (beauty) according to its meaning, but, currently language is mainly used in poetic speech; beautiful; 2) beauty (beautiful, elegant, attractive, charming happy look; attractiveness, beauty; pictorial beauty; softness;)[9].

The concept of "ugliness" (unattractiveness, not beautiful) can be considered from two points of view. From the first narrow approach to its consideration, understanding "ugly" only as "not beautiful" can be considered as the opposite of the beautiful, its denial. Second, by taking a broader approach, it means that it is considered as the concept of "ugly". But, even with a broad concept, first of all, the concept of "ugliness" is manifested in connection with the concept of "niceness", "beauty", as well as the concept of "beauty".

The term "ugliness" (ugly, unpleasant, terrible, strange, crooked, disordered, bad, nervous, scary; stupid, dirty, sad, etc.) is the aesthetic category "beautiful" (beautiful, attractive, niceness, slightly, pleasant, pleasantness, delicacy, elegance, beauty, attractiveness, charm) it is also widely used in literary studies. "Ugly" is defined in the "Thesis of the Terminological Dictionary of Literary Studies" edited by Rusova: "an aesthetic category opposite to the beautiful; it serves to identify and evaluate ugly objects and reality phenomena[10].

In fact, this definition can be considered complete, because it takes into account the ability of "ugliness" to violate the concept of "beauty", which is, in our opinion, the main characteristic. "Ugliness" is defined as "displeasing to the senses", "prone to anger or threatening bad feelings", "morally reprehensible", "horrifying", "depraved and abnormal".

The main objects chosen for our research are "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" [1-5] and McMillan "Annotated Dictionary of the English Language" [2]. In the process of studying the first source, we created a written and electronic index of words specific to the concepts of "beauty/ugliness". The results of our studies showed that the words related to the "beauty/ugliness" concept in the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" are 42 in volume 1 of the dictionary, 49 related to ugliness, 75 related to beauty in volume 2, 31 related to ugliness, and related to beauty in volume 3. We witnessed that there are 95 words, 67 words about ugliness, 75 words about beauty, 49 words about ugliness, 33 words about beauty, 37 words about ugliness, 320 words about beauty, and 242 words about ugliness.

Analysis and results: During the analysis, according to the data, the associative field of the concept of beauty includes the following units: beautiful, elegant, pleasant, quiet, picturesque, decorated, wonderful, charming, harmonious, magnificent, bright, wonderful, polite, delicate, attractive, amazing, etc. A whole class of words within the semantic field of these concepts is described as "beauty-pleasantness" and "ugliness-unpleasantness" because of their appearance, especially in accordance with the ideals of form and proportion.

The concept of "beauty" is represented by the following words: beauty, beauty, pleasant, well-liked, well-liked. Just like in the Uzbek associative series, in English there is power semantics in such lexemes as amazing (attractive, pretty, handsome) and amazing (amazing, nice).

There are synonymous, associative meaning units of the concept of "beauty/ugliness" in both the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek and English languages. The closest associative meaning of beauty in the Uzbek language is the units "beauty", "pleasantness", "slightly", "gentleness", "elegance" and its synonyms are: alif qomat (1; 70), barno (1; 170), barvasta (1; 165), bashang (1; 185), gulandom (1; 517) (synonym- gulbadan), gulbadan (1; 517) (synonym- gulandom), gulgun (1; 518), beautiful (1; 530), beauty (1; 530), beautify (1; 530), gulchegara (1; 521-522) (synonym-Gulchiroy, gulyuz), charming (1; 614), gazelle eye (2; 66), jamila (2; 68), jamal (2; 69), Zebo (2; 145), malakhat (2; 534), lobar (2; 502), nozanin (3; 49), ra'na (3; 359-360), sanobar (3; 441), Sarvinoz (3; 447), sarvqomat (sarv+qomat) (3; 447), suluv (3; 586), parrot (4; 248), parrot (dek) (4; 248), khusroy (4; 433), khussurat (4; 433), hur (5; 563), hurliqo (hurliqo) (5; 563), hurliqo (5; 563), husn (5; 565) in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language"[1] as stated, they are applied to the conduct or behavior of persons or things.

The closest associative meaning of ugliness in the Uzbek language is the units "unpleasantness", "ugliness" and its synonyms: abgor (1; 26), ablah (1; 27), avbosh (1; 29), ajiva (1; 44), alvasti (1; 68), badbashara (1; 133), badburush (1; 133), badgo'y (1; 136), badnamo (1; 136), badnuskha (1; 136-137), badro'y (1; 137), badsurat (1; 137), badchegara (1; 137), badqovaq (1; 138), bangibashara (1; 165), banginusha, bes'anaqay (1; 237), bujur (1; 361), baqaburun (1; 185), bakakoz (1; 185), davangi (1; 536), dilgir (1; 614), gazanda (1; 475), unpleasant (2; 55), disgusting (2; 94), ipirisqi (2; 223), irganch (2; 224), irkit (2; 225), iskirt (2; 40), not agreeable (2; 347), sightless (2; 467), sightless (2; 468), nokas (3; 52), pajmurda (3; 199), palagda (3; 208), pachava (3; 242), razil (3; 342), rasva (3; 351), ro'daro (3; 404), pachak (3; 242) (4; 493), only (5; 110), naughty (5; 116), mischief (noun) (5; 116), dissimilar (5; 186), vile (5; 197) vile (5; 197), beginning (5; 226), rude (5; 411), rude (noun) (5; 412), kors (5; 414), korslik (noun) (5; 414) husnziz (5; 566); etc., as stated in "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" [1], they are applied to the behavior or behavior of people or things.

Also, such lexical units as beauty (attractiveness, cuteness), kahimtoy (attractive, sweet) and ugliness (unpleasantness, blindness), mashum (ominous, threatening) can be considered close to the center of the semantic field of concepts. Accordingly, the exact original forms of the concept of "beauty/ugliness" are not often used, but synonyms that are within the main semantic meaning of these words are used.

Conclusion/Recommendations: In conclusion, it should be noted that the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" and the "MacMillan English Annotated Dictionary", as well as a multifaceted analysis of their interpretation and meaning, show the similar use of vocabulary related to the concepts of "beauty" and "ugliness" in the Uzbek and English languages. Made it possible to identify different aspects and different variants of words. The information presented and analyzed in the article is very important for lexicography and translation studies, which are important branches of linguistics.

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